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Circular Economy Design Forum
– Introducing Entrepreneurial Mindset and Circularity to Teaching

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ABSTRACT

The Circular Economy Design Forum (CEDF) is an EIT RawMaterials educational project aimed at incorporating an entrepreneurial mind-set into engineering education, particularly in topics related to circular economy (CE). As part of this initiative, a new course was developed as a platform to promote a dialog between students, industry and academia. To use this educational platform effectively, a “Training the trainers” event was organized where teaching staff learned how to integrate an entrepreneurial mind-set into courses with technical content and how to support student innovation capabilities. In this paper, the objective is to explore the impact on the mind-set and motivation of students when: i) a circular thinking is promoted through iterative project work within the circular economy context, and ii) a customer-centric approach is incorporated in an engineering course, by letting the students identify real industrial needs together with stakeholders. According to the student’s feedback, most of the participants (15/18) felt that the course supported well their learning on CE topics and enhanced their study motivation. However, it was also evident that additional support is needed for timid students that have trouble contacting stakeholders directly.

Conference Key Areas: Sustainability and Engineering Education, Curriculum Development, Skills and Engineering Education

Keywords: Circular Economy, Entrepreneurial Mindset, Project work, Industrial Collaboration

INTRODUCTION

The European Institute of Innovation and Technology (EIT) is a European initiative supporting innovators and entrepreneurs in the creation of solutions to tackle some of the most pressing societal challenges. One of such topics requiring attention is the increasing demand for raw materials, resulting of the continuous growth in world population and the demand of manufactured products per capita. The EIT RawMaterials Knowledge Innovation Community (KIC) was created with that aim, also supporting educational programs. In addition, the EU framework for education and training 2020 (ET2020) points strengthening entrepreneurship competencies as a strategic objective, and promotion of excellence in teaching as well as sustainable investment in education as priority areas [1]. Education has an important role in improving the entrepreneurship competencies and mind-set, especially for young people [2].

“Circular Economy” (CE) is one of the concepts that has drawn most attention in the area of raw materials production in recent years. CE aims at alleviating the need for primary raw materials in a sustainable manner by maintaining the intrinsic value of raw materials through efficient recycling practices. However, to understand and apply the main concepts of CE in industry, multidisciplinary ideas are required. As value generation lies at the core of the CE concept, an entrepreneurial mind-set of the actors involved in the materials production cycle is required. This need led to the “Circular Economy Design Forum” (CEDF), an educational project funded by EIT RawMaterials.

The CEDF offers an innovative approach as it started with the premise that the teaching staff in engineering education programs are not typically familiar with the basic aspects of entrepreneurship. Thus, this project offered a training session for teaching staff (in December 2016) and produced an entrepreneurial education “toolbox” to support the course development. In this event, staff members were introduced to customer-based thinking and other relevant entrepreneurship concepts.

In engineering education, problem-based learning [3] with the use of project work is a popular approach that is believed to promote the creativity of students [4]. However, in most cases, the students are typically assigned a pre-defined problem to be solved applying the main concepts of the course. In this kind of approach, it is not uncommon that the students start looking for an answer based on what they think will satisfy the teacher, thus limiting the development of creative learning. Furthermore, in real engineering work life, the search for solutions for pre-defined problems is seldom the case.

In contrast to the typical “linear” problem solving education, we aimed at implementing the CE philosophy in education and think rather circularly. For the student project work, this can be implemented in a form where the students discover a problem by themselves. To find a real working case, the students are forced to reach out to clients and stakeholders, making this a customer-centric approach to learning. Once the problem is identified, a potential solution can be proposed, but then, together with a mentor, the problem-solution pair needs to be evaluated and redefined iteratively, to find both a better problem definition and an attractive solution.

After various cycles – the most relevant problem can be discovered. This iterative process thus becomes a tool to foster innovation.

An entrepreneurial mind-set is not only valid for the creation of new ventures and start-ups but should be considered a general skill [2]. One crucial difference from learning based on pre-defined problem solving, is that entrepreneurs actively work to identify the problems that need solving in the first place. Thus, this skill is important for all engineers, whether they work in their own company or as employees [5,6]. An entrepreneurial mind-set can be learned via real development projects that are initiated by an active discussion with stakeholders to understand their needs [7]. Evidently, for this process, the students need careful advice and instructions on how to proceed, as it might feel scary and therefore, the students need constant checkpoints and transparent feedback of the evaluation process [8] to find the right motivation. The teacher may not be in charge on the project, but is still very much so in the educational process.

1 DEVELOPMENT OF THE CIRCULAR ECONOMY DESIGN FORUM

Effective implementation of an entrepreneurial mind-set into engineering teaching cannot be obtained by adding a few dedicated contact sessions in a course, but rather as a mind-set involving teaching style and assignments. The objective of this paper is to study how to implement these concepts to an engineering course having technical content, namely, the understanding of CE in raw materials processing. To ensure this integration, prior to the planning of the CEDF course content, a training event for teaching staff was organised to share good practices in the development of course structures involving entrepreneurship.

1.1 Training the trainers event

As mentioned in the Introduction section, the CEDF project was used as a training platform on which the teaching staff from various universities could learn from experience to work within an entrepreneurial framework. The staff worked in teams to learn how innovation-driven projects can be directed and how to provide effective feedback. The learning outcomes for this event:

- Help teachers add hands-on, entrepreneurial elements to their teaching
- (Re)design a course from the teacher's local university to include elements of entrepreneurship in an interactive and hypothesis based approach

The event took place on December 2016, and was hosted by Aalto Ventures Program (AVP), a program within Aalto University with a strong history on the teaching of entrepreneurial skills at various levels of higher education. Nonetheless, AVP had no previous history on training educators in such a systematic way, upon which future training workshops can be provided. The timetable of the event and the themes discussed in the workshops can be seen in Table 1.

Table 1. Workshop topics for the CEDF “Training the Trainers” event.

Day 1	Day 2	Day 3
Intro to the workshop Pre-work video session	Lecture: Circular Economy by Markus Reuter	Teaching event with local students
Morning WS: “Student assignments and uncertainty”	Morning WS: “Feedback and teacher presence”	Student presentations
Afternoon WS: “Class culture + learning process”	Afternoon WS: “Learning objectives + grading + work load”	Feedback and discussion of the event
Own Course development	Own Course development	-

For the first two days the teachers were divided into teams that used one of the courses identified during the preliminary tasks as working examples. At the beginning of each workshop, the experiences obtained during a similar integration of entrepreneurial mind-set to a pilot Capstone course named Materials Processes and Synthesis (MPS, held Fall 2016), were introduced and reflected upon. Afterwards, the topic of the workshop was processed in the context of the developed courses in a team. Feedback on the content development but also on the team performance was provided to give the teachers an impression on how it feels to receive feedback. Thus, it became clear that constructive feedback for the students is important, since a negative or extremely critical environment does not encourage innovation.

During the last training day, a group of volunteer students from the MPS course (i.e., who had already experienced an entrepreneurial mind-set teaching) was invited to work on a case study. The task for the students was to develop a Stakeholders Analysis for sustainable business ideas and they were guided by the trained staff. Various iterations were carried out based on the feedback provided by the trainers. On the closing sessions, both the students and the staff members received feedback from each other and from the facilitators on their performance (*Fig. 1*). Since engineering teachers and professors tend to work with projects where is only a “one way to the solution”, it was pointed out that the trainers tend to direct the students to the path they had considered appropriate. It is important to be able to guide the students at the direction they had decided and only set proper frameworks to encourage the students to identify their own path, however difficult that might be.

Teachers liked:

“Feedback provided new way of thinking and tools”

“Being as a student”

“The active way of teaching”

“Good experience the student group mentoring”

“The way of how the class were performed”

“I also liked the teachers giving creative feedbacks”

Fig. 1. Feedback session with the students and teachers [Photo by R. Serna] as well as written feedback provided by the participants.

1.2 Selected teaching methods and their alignment

With the aim of creating a “forum” as its name suggests, the overall approach for the CEDF course was that, instead of the classical “lecture + exercise” model, a dialogue-based education was promoted. We invited experts on the field of CE from different organizations willing to engage the students into considering the CE concept from different angles. To promote the discussion of the various aspects of CE and promoting a dialogue with industry, the teaching and assessment methods were carefully selected to support the intended learning outcomes (ILO). The ILOs presented in *Table 2* are aligned with the teaching methods and assessments as suggested by Biggs and Tangs [9].

Table 2. The ILOs aligned with the teaching method and assessments.

ILOs	Teaching method	Assessment
The student has learned the main concepts of CE and their relevance in the production and processing of metallic raw materials	Workshops (Introduction, Re-Think, Sitra), group discussion, Excursion	Circular Economy Essay 1 and 2, Project work
Developed entrepreneurial thinking from a CE perspective	Workshops (Re-Start and introduction) Group discussion	Circular Economy Essay 2, Project work
Modeled innovative recycling processes to determine their feasibility and environmental impact	HSC training, Re-Act workshop	Disassemble report (Re-ACT)
Applied their knowledge to solve project relevant for industry, including aspects of economic analysis	Re-Act workshop, Project work	Project work
Worked in a multicultural team	Project work	Project work

The largest individual assessment method was the 2 CE Essays where the first was written at the beginning of the course to determine their initial level of understanding of CE, and the relevance of entrepreneurship and value creation on it. The second essay was prepared at the end of the course as a reflection to learning. Both Essays included a graphical representation of CE. The assumption in this study was that the depth of the CE concepts in the second essay should reflect the efforts that each student had invested to the course. In total, the essays formed 25 % of the total grade and the rest 25 % by other individual tasks. Additional activities to support the lectures included a hands-on workshop on WEEE dismantling and an excursion to an industrial recycling facility.

Thus, the group project work used to evaluate how the students apply the concepts of CE provided the rest 50 % of the grade. The aim of this study was to discover if the students could generate a dialogue to industry and identify issues on CE that address industrial needs and have the potential to create some added value. Another hypothesis in this work was that when the students are required to identify a stakeholder company and a topic by themselves, they will feel more engaged. This also puts in practice the idea that with an entrepreneurial mind-set, relevant problems are discovered through dialogue with clients [7]. Four feedback sessions were set between teacher and the student groups to assess the problem-solution pair in an iterative manner.

2 LESSONS LEARNED FROM THE CEDF COURSE

In Spring 2017, a pilot CEDF course was held with the participation of 18 students: 15 from Master's and 3 from Doctoral level. The participants were students from different disciplines, including process engineering, materials science, chemistry, mechanical engineering, physics, business and arts. In addition, the students formed a multicultural group, having representatives from various nationalities.

As the CEDF course was quite short (5 ECTS) it was necessary to maximize the active learning process during the contact sessions and minimize information sharing by lecturing. A detailed schedule of the course is presented in *Fig. 2*. The black text indicates the topics of workshops, while the blue text shows the project work milestones. There was also relevant literature provided to the students that they could select according to their specific interests and use as reference a material in the essays. By week 2, an industrial process simulation software (HSC SIM 9, Outotec) was introduced as a tool that could be utilized in the project work to assess the resource efficiency and footprint of selected technological business opportunities [10]. This was utilized by 3 out of the 5 groups in their project work.

Fig. 2. CEDF structure: black text describes the events and blue project milestones.

For the personal assessment, students prepared two essays to show if the CE concepts had been strengthened during the course. These essays also involved visualization as exemplified in in *Fig. 3*, where it can be clearly seen that at the beginning of the course, most of the students had implemented just linear or basic round visualization for CE.

Fig. 3. Example of a student's visualization of the CE before and after the course.

In comparison, after the course, all the students had implemented a round visualization but with iterative nature. In most of the second visualizations, scenarios that are more complex were presented: waste creation at different stages, additional energy input, social and economic aspects. New ways to utilize end-of-life products were taken into consideration and the possibilities for new business models like leasing or renting were considered. Especially with the students that participated in most of the workshops, numerous references were included in the essays and the conceptual understanding of CE was deep. It is worth mentioning that at no point was any memorization encouraged (essays were prepared from home).

Each team selected a company that they interviewed on their ideas and needs on CE solutions. The selected companies represented wider range of industry than if selected merely by the teaching staff: from metal industry to real estate business. As was aimed in the study, all groups were able to identify interesting development targets by the interviews; however, all topics were scoped during the mentoring sessions. In the end, the projects proposed different improvements to CE practices in the selected companies, for instance by utilization of side or waste streams, improving logistics efficiency or new business models (leasing).

From the student feedback, it was observed that most of the students (15 out of 18) stated that the teaching methods supported their learning and their study motivation had improved slightly or notably during the course. The students also pointed out that they felt very engaged in the project because they felt excitement about developing a project with a typical entrepreneurial approach. In addition, they considered that the course content was very relevant for their future career and they enjoyed working at the interface with industry. Admittedly, some students expressed that this approach felt intimidating and is more demanding than their typical Master's degree courses.

3 CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

The aim of this project was to incorporate an entrepreneurial mind-set to engineering courses having technical content, and to discover if this approach supports the development of circular thinking required in CE. In the first approach the participants prepared project works where they interviewed stakeholders and identified problems. All groups found projects that were very innovative and provided interesting CE solutions, thus some groups needed additional mentoring to narrow down their topic. According to the student feedback, most of the participants felt more engaged in these projects than with regular pre-defined projects and reported that this course clearly enhanced their study motivation. In the second approach, reading material and workshops with stakeholders were provided to enhance the learning of concepts on CE and this clearly influenced on the students thinking, as reflected by the second essays and especially in their more intricate visualisations.

For the teaching staff, one key finding during the course is how multidisciplinary the CE concepts are. If real innovation on this area is needed, multidisciplinary teams are required to provide solutions from engineering, business and design perspectives. In the future, the forum may be developed towards a platform where different stakeholders meet and discuss the challenges of CE. As additional material, videos created as part of the CEDF project describing the experience of introducing entrepreneurial aspects in engineering teaching are available in the following links:

Ideas before the course: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=BsILM0n2wG4>

Ideas after the course: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=s3JjNLAVRps>

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